

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON CRACKING AND DEFLECTION BEHAVIOUR OF RC BEAMS STRENGTHENED WITH EBR CFRP LAMINATES UNDER DIFFERENT PRE-LOADING CONDITIONS

Luis Jimenez, Universidad Católica Boliviana San Pablo, Bolivia, ljimenez@ucb.edu.bo

Alba Codina, Universitat de Girona, Spain, alba.codina@udg.edu

Younes Jahani, Universitat de Girona, Spain, younes.yahani@udg.edu

Ricardo Perera, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain, ricardo.perera@upm.es

Cristina Barris, Universidad de Girona, Spain, cristina.barris@udg.edu

ABSTRACT

This study experimentally evaluates the influence of a pre-cracked stage on the deflection and cracking behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) beams strengthened with externally bonded CFRP laminates. Three RC beams were loaded until their service load, then strengthened and tested until rupture, while three other identical beams, were strengthened and directly tested until failure. The midspan deflection and a total of 145 cracks were studied through the Digital Image Correlation. The experimental results were compared with sectional analysis theoretical predictions, while crack spacing and width were compared to Ceroni and Pecce proposal. Main findings indicate that the pre-cracked stage does not have a clear influence on the final deformational behaviour of the beam.

KEYWORDS

EB; deflection; crack width; DIC; serviceability; experimental study

INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) have been proven to be excellent materials for strengthening Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures. Considering that RC elements strengthened with CFRP perform different to RC structures, design procedures and limitations established in codes and guidelines need to be reviewed to certify a correct and appropriate design. In that regard, the assessment of crack width and the influence of a pre-cracked stage is still under discussion.

CFRP reinforcement provides higher stiffness to RC beams, leading to lower deflections and crack widths. Moreover, the additional shear stress transfer between concrete and CFRP provides also a more diffuse crack pattern that also leads to smaller crack spacings and narrower crack widths (*fib* Bulletin 90 2019). This crack bridging effect was experimentally observed in several investigations, either for Externally Bonded (EB) CFRP (Matthys 2000, Tripi et al. 2000) or for Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) CFRP reinforcement (Barris et al. 2023). Al-Salaawani et al. (2017) found a dependency of the experimental crack width in RC beams strengthened with Externally Bonded (EB) CFRP with the amount of internal steel reinforcement and with the ratio of FRP plate to beam width. Zomorodian et al (2016), in turn, found a relationship between cracking behaviour of RC ties strengthened with EB CFRP and the wrapping scheme and FRP reinforcement ratios. One main concern for strengthened beams after being in service is the influence of the pre-loading stage on the final crack width and spacing. In this regard, no experimental results can be found in literature, which leads to uncertainty about its behaviour.

The use of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique to evaluate crack patterns in RC beams has been shown to be a promising technique, thanks to objective and systematic measure of crack spacing and crack width (Barris et al. 2017, Zomorodian et al. 2016). Nevertheless, the use of this technique generates a huge amount of data that needs special software to be processed and analysed, which can be unhandy and weighty to manage.

The present paper presents the preliminary results of an experimental programme on EB CFRP RC beams designed to study their cracking behaviour under different strengthening and loading conditions. Three unstrengthened RC beams have been tested until their service load, unloaded, strengthened and

tested until failure, while other three RC beams, with the identical configuration of the previous ones, have been directly strengthened and tested until failure, to evaluate the influence of the pre-cracked condition on the deformational and cracking behaviour. Data obtained has been analysed following a subroutine that consists of data extraction from DIC generated files, numerical analysis and discussion of results in a Matlab code. The results obtained, in terms of deflection, crack width and crack spacing are presented and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Beam design philosophy

An experimental programme with a total of six beam specimens was designed, with each of the specimens having different reinforcement and testing conditions. The design philosophy included three groups of beams:

- Group 0 (R): RC beams without any CFRP reinforcement, that were tested until their service load to serve as reference specimens. These beams were tested under an increasing monotonic load, followed by three loading cycles which had the purpose of simulating service loading conditions on each beam. The test was performed between 28 to 32 days after casting,
- Group 1 (S1): After loading and unloading, specimens of Group 0 were removed from the testing frame and strengthened with EB CFRP, thus becoming Group 1 beams. After 10 days of curing of the adhesive, Group 1 specimens were tested monotonically until failure.
- Group 2 (S2): Group 2 was formed by three RC beams that were internally reinforced with the same reinforcement ratio of Groups 0-1, and were strengthened with the same CFRP reinforcement ratio of Group 1. These beams were strengthened after curing of concrete and were tested until failure at the same age of Group 1 specimens. Geometrically, Group 2 beams were identical to Group 1 specimens, but their load history was different, as they were tested without any previous loading.

In each Group, three beam specimen types were defined: one with an internal steel reinforcement of 2Φ8 mm and two with an internal steel reinforcement of 2Φ10 mm. The specimen with 2Φ8 mm along with one of 2Φ10 mm were strengthened with one laminate of 50x1.4mm, while the remaining specimen with 2Φ10 mm was strengthened with two laminates of the same dimensions.

Table 1: Tensile reinforcement details (Steel and FRP) of specimens

Group	Specimen	A_{s1}	A_f	ρ_{s1} [%]	ρ_f [%]	d_{s1} [mm]	P_{max} [kN]	Failure mode	δ_{max} [mm]
Group 0	R-D8-1L	2Φ8	-	0.40	-	140.0	14.2	-	6.5
	R-D10-1L	2Φ10		0.62		139.0	19.9	-	7.9
	R-D10-2L						19.7	-	7.5
Group 1	S1-D8-1L	2Φ8	50x1.4	0.40	0.28	140.0	38.0	Debonding	11.7
	S1-D10-1L	2Φ10	2x50x1.4	0.62		139.0	59.5	Debonding	18.8
	S1-D10-2L				58.7		Debonding	12.5	
Group 2	S2-D8-1L	2Φ8	50x1.4	0.40	0.28	140.0	45.2	Debonding	15.8
	S2-D10-1L	2Φ10	2x50x1.4	0.62		139.0	54.9	Debonding	17.0
	S2-D10-2L				55.1		Debonding	11.8	

In Table 1, the details of steel and CFRP tensile reinforcement, in terms of reinforcement cross-section (A_{s1} and A_f for steel and FRP, respectively), reinforcement ratio (ρ_{s1} and ρ_f for steel and FRP, respectively) and effective depth of steel reinforcement, d_{s1} , are given. Furthermore, the maximum load attained in the test, P_{max} , together with its corresponding midspan deflection, δ_{max} , is also provided. It should be mentioned that for Group 1 (R) beams, these values indicate the considered service load, while for Group 1 (S1) and Group 2 (S2) beams, the values correspond to the failure condition. Service load was assumed to be the load level at which maximum theoretical concrete compressive stress attained 45% of its compressive strength. Finally, the denomination of beam specimens followed the

pattern X-Y-Z, where X stands for Group denomination (R for Group 0, S1 for Group 1 and S2 for Group 2). Y is the diameter of internal reinforcement (D8 for 8mm, and D10 for 10mm), and Z stands for the number of EB CFRP laminates (1L for one laminate and 2L for two laminates). Reference (Group 0) beams were also named with the -Z level tag to distinguish how the specimen was later strengthened (either with one or two laminates).

Test setup and instrumentation

All specimens were internally reinforced with two top longitudinal steel bars of 6mm diameter. Steel stirrups of 8 mm were placed every 100 mm along the beam to avoid shear failure. Loads applied were located at locations distanced 550 mm from each support. A hydraulic jack applied the load to a rigid steel beam, which in turn transmitted the load to the beam on two specific points (Figure 1, Figure 2). The test was performed under a displacement control mode at a rate of 0.60 mm/min.

The applied load was measured thanks to a load cell placed under the hydraulic actuator. Three displacement transducers were used to measure the mid-span deflection, one placed at the mid-span section and two on the supports.

Figure 1: Test setup and dimensions (all dimensions in mm)

Material properties

All specimens were cast from the same concrete batch. The compressive strength (f_c) and modulus of elasticity (E_c) were obtained from cylinder tests according to UNE-EN 12390-2 (2003) and ASTM C 469-87 (2010) standards with resulting average values of 23.88 MPa and 29.31 GPa respectively. The standard deviation (SD) for each property was equal to 0.41 MPa for f_c and 1.02 GPa for E_c . The steel reinforcement had a modulus of elasticity of 200 GPa and a yield strength of 500 MPa.

The mechanical properties of the CFRP laminate were determined according to ISO 527-5 (2009). The modulus of elasticity (E_f) was 169.94 GPa (SD = 9.25 GPa). The ultimate tensile strength (f_{tu}) was equal to 2250 MPa according to the manufacturer.

Measurement of crack width and crack spacing

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used to identify and measure cracks on the pure moment zone of each beam. Four high-resolution cameras with a resolution of 2452×2056 pixels were placed at a distance of 950 mm from the beam front surface. These cameras covered a total length of the central 1100 mm, corresponding to the pure bending zone of the beam. Surface treatment, consisting of the application of white paint followed by black spray paint over it, was applied on the beam's front face. Speckle pattern efficiency was then determined by measuring the mean intensity gradient (MIG) (Pan et al., 2010), with an average value equal to 11.7 value associated to each camera. Lens opening was equal to f/4.2 on all lenses used, exposition time for all cameras was equal to 1.5 ms, and the distance between cameras was equal to 30 cm. VIC 2D software was used to correlate all information and obtain the full field of in-plane displacements on the treated surface of the beam. Images with a mean conversion factor of 0.144 mm/px were correlated using the Normalised Sum of Square Differences (NSSD) method. A subset size of 21x21 pixels and step size of 5 pixels were used for this correlation.

Figure 2: Experimental setup

The detection of cracks was obtained from the experimental data collected from DIC at the central length of 1100 mm. Strain fields were used to determine the correct location of each crack. Crack spacing was calculated as the distance between two consecutive cracks at the height of the internal steel tensile reinforcement. Crack opening threshold for crack spacing was specified as 0.05 mm in order to appreciate the growth of the spacing function. Crack width was evaluated as the increasing distance between two points, each one separated 10 mm from the centre of the crack (Eqs.1 to 3),

$$w_i = d_f - d_o \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$d_o = \sqrt{(x_{c,r} - x_{c,l})^2 + (y_{c,r} - y_{c,l})^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$d_f = \sqrt{\left((x_{c,r} + u_{c,r}) - (x_{c,l} + u_{c,l})\right)^2 + \left((y_{c,r} + v_{c,r}) - (y_{c,l} + v_{c,l})\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where w_i is the crack width value, d_f and d_o are distanced measured at the displaced and initial position respectively. The values of both pairs of coordinates, one being $x_{c,r}$ and $y_{c,r}$ and the other $x_{c,l}$ and $y_{c,l}$ are calibrated coordinates located on the point located to the right and left of the crack respectively. The calibrated horizontal and vertical displacements of the points located to the right and left of the crack are described as $u_{c,r}$ and $v_{c,r}$ for the former, and $u_{c,l}$ and $v_{c,l}$ for the latter.

There are three instances of calculation for crack spacing. First, for each crack identified along the beam, the load at which each crack opens is computed and saved. Second, the crack spacing is calculated for all cracks present on the beam using a common coordinate system for all cameras. Finally with the information obtained from the two previous instances the spacing between cracks that open is calculated with Eq. 4, using a routine that saves each spacing in a vector, from which the maximum, mean and minimum values are calculated (for each crack i and $i+1$ a crack spacing value is determined). Crack spacing growth and y-axis coordinate data were ignored because their inclusion did not provide a significant change and only made calculations heavier and harder to compute.

$$S_{value} = x_i - x_{i+1} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON WITH THEORETICAL PREDICTIONS

Load – midspan deflection

Experimental response

The experimental load – midspan deflection behaviour was obtained for each beam specimen from the results of transducers and it is represented in Figure 3. It is observed that beams of Group 0 and 2 (unstrengthened beams, R, and beams initially strengthened and tested without any preloading cycles, S2) presented an initial similar stiff behaviour due to their non-cracked nature, while Group 1 beams (those strengthened after loading cycles, S1) did not present this initial response, as they had been already cracked. By comparison between beams of Groups 0 and 2, it was observed that the cracking load increased with the application of the strengthening system. After initiation of cracking, unstrengthened and strengthened beams followed different stiffness patterns, as expected, being the strengthened ones significantly stiffer. Group 2 beams tended follow the same stiffness pattern to that of beams of Group 1 (beams strengthened after being tested) once the crack pattern had developed. It should be mentioned that any residual deflection from Group 0 beams was not registered, hence, the initial deflection in Group 2 beams equalled zero. Finally, it is worth noticing that yielding load could not be identified in any case: for Group 0 beams, loading cycles did not reach in any case the yield load, while in Groups 1 and 2, beams failed prematurely before yielding.

Figure 3: Experimental and theoretical load-midspan deflection curves for (a) D8-1L specimens, (b) D10-1L specimens, (c) D10-2L specimens.

Theoretical predictions

The experimental load-midspan deflection response was compared with the theoretical response obtained from a sectional analysis. Sectional analysis in this paper assumed Bernoulli hypothesis (plane sections before bending remain plane after bending), perfect bond between materials and all constitutive laws of materials known (Barris et al. 2020). Furthermore, weighted average between cracked and uncracked sections was applied following Eurocode 2 (CEN 2004) approach. The results of the analytical predictions are shown in Figure 3 together with the experimental results for comparison purposes. A general close correlation between experimental and theoretical responses can be observed up to experimental failure. Furthermore, it can be seen that none of the strengthened beams achieved a load value higher than the one corresponding to the theoretical yielding point of steel. This was due to debonding taking place due to the setup configuration of the test, which is out of the scope of this paper.

Crack patterns

Crack patterns were detected using strain profiles of pictures obtained from DIC data. In Figure 4, crack patterns of all beams are shown for the maximum attained load using the strain field (Table 1), which was in all cases far from the theoretical ultimate load, and close to the yielding load of internal steel reinforcement. For comparison purposes, specimens of each beam type are plotted together.

Figure 4: Crack patterns of beams: (a) D8-1L, (b) D10-1L, and (c) D10-2L (Top picture corresponding to Group 0, middle picture to Group 1 and bottom picture to Group 2).

In non-strengthened (Group 0) beams, a low number of cracks accompanied by high crack spacing was observed. For strengthened beams of Group 1, it was observed that cracks previously opened during loading before strengthening were reopened with loading (these cracks are represented with red arrows

in Figure 4), and additional cracks were formed in between the original ones. However, the residual value of the crack previously formed during the loading cycles was not computed in Group 1 beams. For Group 2 beams, without a previous loading cycle, the obtained number of cracks was similar to that of Group 1, which had a previous loading history before strengthening.

Crack spacing

Experimental response

Figure 5 shows the evolution of experimental crack spacing with load. A crack width threshold of 0.05 mm was determined to evaluate spacing between cracks. Mean, maximum and minimum values were calculated for each load value, however, in this paper only the mean value is drawn for verification purposes. In general, it is observed that crack spacing diminishes with the load, as expected, until the stabilized cracking load. Crack spacing of Group 1 (S1) and Group 2 (S2) beams tend to similar values, indicating that the load history, in this case, is not determining a significant difference in this parameter.

Theoretical predictions

Experimental results are compared with the theoretical value of the mean crack spacing according to Ceroni and Pecce (2009), $s_{rm,th}$:

$$s_{rm,th} = 20 + 4 * \frac{A_{c,eff}^{0.5} * \phi_s}{A_s^{0.75} + \left(\frac{A_f * E_f}{E_s}\right)^{0.75}} \quad [mm] \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where $s_{rm,th}$ is the mean crack spacing at serviceability condition, $A_{c,eff}$ is the effective area of concrete in tension surrounding the steel reinforcement following Eurocode 2 (2004) recommendations, ϕ_s is the reinforcement steel bar diameter, A_f and E_f are the reinforcement area and the elastic modulus of the FRP laminate, respectively, A_s and E_s are the reinforcement area and the elastic modulus of steel, respectively. It can be seen that, in all cases, the experimental mean crack spacing tends to the theoretical mean value once stabilized cracking has been achieved.

Figure 5: Experimental and theoretical crack spacing for (a) D8-1L beams, (b) D10-1L beams and (c) D10-2L beams

Crack width

Experimental response

Crack width was obtained for all cracks appearing in the pure bending zone in all beams. From them, the minimum, mean and maximum values were obtained, and the mean value is represented in Figure 6. As observed, there is a slight increase in the cracking moment of concrete for strengthened (S2) beams with respect to the unstrengthened (R) ones. After cracking, the strengthened (S2) beams presented a significantly higher stiffness compared to the unstrengthened (R) ones, deriving in narrower crack width values. Finally, by comparison between strengthened beams with different loading histories (S1 and S2), it was observed that for the cases strengthened with one laminate (D8-1L and D10-1L), the mean crack width of the strengthened after loading (S1) beams tended to the strengthened without loading (2) beams. However, for the specimens strengthened with 2 laminates (D10-2L), the mean crack width of S1 specimen was higher than that of S2.

Figure 6: Experimental and theoretical mean crack width for (a) D8-1L beams, (b) D10-1L beams and (c) D10-2L beams

Theoretical predictions

The theoretical predictions obtained by Ceroni and Pecce (2009) approach, and adopted in *fib* Bulletin 90 (2019) as simplified approach are also plotted for comparison purposes. Following this approach, crack width at the height of internal steel reinforcement can be calculated as:

$$w_m = s_{rm}(\varepsilon_{sm} - \varepsilon_{cm}) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\varepsilon_{sm} - \varepsilon_{cm} = \frac{\sigma_s - k_t \frac{f_{ctm}}{\rho_{eff,eq}} (1 + \alpha_s \rho_{eff,eq})}{E_s} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where $\varepsilon_{sm} - \varepsilon_{cm}$ is the mean strain difference between steel reinforcement and concrete between cracks, σ_s is the tensile stress in the steel reinforcement under service loading assuming a cracked section, k_t is a factor dependent on the duration of the load (and considered equal to 0.6 in this study), f_{ctm} is the mean value of the tensile strength of concrete, α_s is the modular ratio of steel (equal to E_s/E_c being E_c the modulus of elasticity of concrete), and $\rho_{eff,eq}$ is the total equivalent reinforcement ratio with respect to the effective area of concrete in tension, and equal to:

$$\rho_{eq,ef} = \frac{A_s}{A_{c,ef}} + \frac{E_f}{E_s} \frac{A_f}{A_{c,ef}} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where $A_{c,ef}$ is calculated according to Eurocode 2 (2004). From comparison with experimental data, it is seen that this theoretical approach generally provides an underestimation of crack width. However, this approach was empirically adjusted from an experimental database on RC beams strengthened with EB CFRP sheets, which present lower values of reinforcement ratio, indicating that more data would be needed for broader assessment of crack width in EB CFRP RC flexural members.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the experimental outcomes of the deformational and cracking behaviour of RC beams strengthened with EB CFRP laminates through an experimental programme. Three RC beams with two different internal reinforcement ratios were tested under their service load and strengthened afterwards, then tested until failure. Furthermore, three other beams, with identical geometrical and mechanical properties, were strengthened without being previously damaged and tested until failure. The experimental deflection was compared with theoretical results using sectional analysis, while the crack spacing and crack width were compared with Ceroni & Pecce (2009) proposal.

From the results obtained and shown above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The deflection response of specimens strengthened after damage (S1 specimens) was close to that of specimens strengthened without any damage (S2 specimens). Furthermore, theoretical predictions using sectional analysis generally provided close results to the experimental response.
- Cracks developed during loading in group 0 beams (R specimens) re-appeared after the specimen was strengthened (S1 specimens). In strengthened specimens (S1 and S2), higher number of cracks was observed due to better shear transfer between tensile reinforcements and concrete.
- The mean crack spacing decreased with the increase of load, until reaching the stabilized cracking phase. At stabilized cracking, crack spacing was well predicted by Ceroni & Pecce (2009) approach. Crack spacing for S1 and S2 specimens was generally very similar.
- For beams strengthened with one laminate (D8-1L and D10-1L), the mean crack width of the strengthened after loading (S1) beams tended to the strengthened without loading (2) beams, but for the specimens strengthened with 2 laminates (D10-2L), the mean crack width of S1 specimen was higher than that of S2. Ceroni & Pecce (2009) approach tended to slightly underestimate the mean crack spacing.

REFERENCES

Al-Saawani MA, El-Sayed AK, Al-Negheimish AI (2017), Crack width prediction for concrete beams strengthened with carbon FRP composites, *Journal of Composites for Construction* 21(5): 04017023.

ASTM C469/C469M (2010) Standard test method for static modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio of concrete in compression. ASTM International

Barris C, Torres L, Vilanova I, Miàs C, Llorens M (2017), Experimental study on crack width and crack spacing for Glass-FRP reinforced concrete beams, *Engineering Structures*, 131, pp.231-242.

Barris C, Sala P, Gómez J, Torres L (2020) Flexural behaviour of FRP reinforced concrete beams strengthened with NSM CFRP strips, *Composite Structures* 241, 112059.

Barris C, Baena M, Jahani Y, Codina A, Torres L (2023), Experimental study on flexural cracking and deformation of reinforced-concrete beams strengthened with NSM FRP reinforcement, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 27(2), 04023006.

CEB-FIP (2019) Bulletin 90. Externally applied FRP reinforcement for concrete structures. *Fédération Internationale du béton* 229 pp.

CEN (2004) Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures – Part 1. 1: General rules and rules for buildings (EN 1992-1-1:2004) 225 pp.

Ceroni F. & Pecce M. (2009). Design provisions for crack spacing and width in RC elements externally bonded with FRP, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 40(1), 17-28.

ISO 527-5 (2009) plastics-determination of tensile properties, part 5: test conditions for unidirectional fibre-reinforced plastic composites. International Organization for Standardization.

Matthys S. (2000) Structural behaviour and design of concrete members strengthened with externally bonded FRP reinforcement. Doctoral thesis, Ghent University, Belgium.

Pan B., Lu Z., Xie H. (2010) Mean intensity gradient: An effective global parameter for quality assessment of the speckle patterns used in digital image correlation. *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, 48(4), pp. 469-477.

Tripi JM, Bakis CE, Boothby TE, Nanni A (2000), Deformation in concrete with external CFRP sheet reinforcement, *ASCE Journal of Composites for Construction*, 4(2): 85-94.

UNE-EN 12390-3 (2003) Testing hardened concrete, part 3: compressive strength of test specimens.

Zomorodian M, Yang G., Belarbi A, Ayoub A (2016), Cracking behaviour and crack width predictions of FRP strengthened RC members under tension, *Engineering Structures* 125, 313-324.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the project PID2020-119015GB-C22 (MCIN/AEI/10.13039/5011000011033) and PID2020-119015GB-C21. The authors also wish to acknowledge the support of S&P Clever Reinforcement Ibérica Lda. For supplying the laminates and adhesive used in this study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.